

EELISA

European University

**EELISA INNOCORE WP5 – “SET UP INITIATIVES FOR
JOINT RESEARCH PROJECTS (ENABLE JOINT RESEARCH)”**

Deliverable D5.5 “Report on Digital Innovation Hubs”

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EELISA InnoCORE Partners

Number	Role	Name in original language	Name in English	Short name	Country
1	COO	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	Technical University of Madrid	UPM	Spain
2	BEN	École Nationale des Ponts et Chaussées	National School of Civil Engineering	ENPC	France
3	BEN	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	Friedrich-Alexander University Erlangen-Nürnberg	FAU	Germany
4	BEN	İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi	Istanbul Technical University	ITU	Turkey
5	BEN	Scuola Normale Superiore	Higher Normal School	SNS	Italy
6	BEN	Scuola Superiore di Studi Universitari e di Perfezionamento Sant'Anna	Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies	SSSA	Italy
7	BEN	Universitatea Politehnica din Bucuresti	Politehnica University of Bucharest	UPB	Romania
8	BEN	Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem	Budapest University of Technology and Economics	BME	Hungary
9	BEN	Université Paris Sciences et Lettres	Université PSL	PSL	France

Alliance members

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Executive summary

EELISA proposes to serve as an academic backbone linking a cohort of European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIHs) and Seal of Excellence (SoE) that have been fostered within the Digital Europe Programme to stimulate the broad uptake of Artificial Intelligence, High Performance Computing (HPC) and Cybersecurity as well as other digital technologies.

This deliverable has the aim to understand possible synergies between EDIH or SoE and the EELISA alliance. Four are the EDIHS that has been analysed in this document, considering the results of the EELISA Survey on European Digital Innovation Hubs.

The EELISA survey on European Digital Innovation Hubs and Seal of Excellence within the EELISA Alliance has the main aim to map the EDIHs within the EELISA Alliance and explore spaces for possible collaboration. The document is organized into 5 sections:

1. the first section is dedicated to an introduction to the EELISA Innocore project;
2. the second section is dedicated to the definition of DIHs and their main characteristics, as well as a brief update on the European situation on these hubs;
3. the third section is related to the results of the questionnaire, analysed for each DIHs in comparison;
4. the fourth section is dedicated to the discussion of ways in which hubs and the alliance can mutually benefit;
5. the last section is related to possible future and long term collaborations.

Following table summarizes the EELISA EDIHs.

Eelisa University	EDIH or SoE	Location and year of establishment	Relation EDIH SoE and University
	SoE Air4S direct connection	Madrid 2018	UPM is lead partner
	EDIH ARTES 5.0 direct connection	Pontedera (Pisa) 2022	SSSA is associated partner of Artes 5.0 and founding partner of Competence center Artes 4.0
 <small>Co-funded by the European Union</small>	EDIH DigiCare indirect connection	Erlangen 2023	Fau is not directly involved, but a premium partner of Medical Valley (one institution responsible for the EDIH)
	EDIH Tuscany X.0 Direct connection	Pisa 2022	SNS and SSSA are funded beneficiaries

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Responsibles for European Digital Innovation Hub Survey

Partner	Acronym	Contact person for
Universidad Politecnica De Madrid	UPM	Isabel Salgueiro, Juan Manuel Muñoz Guijosa
Ecole Nationale Des Ponts Et Chaussees	ENPC	Mustafa SEVIMLI
Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nuernberg	FAU	David Schkade
Istanbul Teknik Universitesi	ITÜ	Hür Bersam Sidal Bolat
Scuola Normale Superiore	SNS	Darya Krasilnikov, Simona Gallerani
Scuola Superiore Di Studi Universitari E Di Perfezionamento S Anna	SSSA	Sara Barsanti, Rossella Raso, Calogero Oddo
Universitatea Politehnica Din Bucuresti	UPB	Dana Violeta Gheroghe, Catalin Negru, Ciprian Dobre
Budapesti Muszaki Es Gazdasagtudományi Egyetem	BME	László Gergely Vigh, Balazs Bokor
Universite Paris Sciences et Lettres	PSL	Antoine Merceir, Soares Fanny

Review and quality check by EELISA

In order to guarantee coordination and complementarity and avoid overlapping between the two projects, the following people from EELISA have been consulted for the production of this deliverable Isabel Salgueiro and Juan Manuel Muñoz Guijosa (UPM) and Rossella Raso (SSSA).

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Glossary- Abbreviations and definitions

(alphabetic order)

CA. Consortium Agreement. The consortium agreement is a private agreement between the beneficiaries, to set out the rights and obligations amongst themselves. (It does NOT involve the European Commission/Agency.)

Communication. Taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its research outputs to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.

Dissemination. The public disclosure of the research outputs by any appropriate means, including by scientific publications in any medium.

Exploitation. The utilisation of research outputs in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.

EELISA Community. The EELISA communities are mission-driven working groups that bring together students, teachers, and researchers from all partner universities with prestigious professionals, grassroots organizations, citizens, private companies, and public institutions to find innovative solutions to real-world challenges.

EELISA Cluster. EELISA Clusters are science-based working groups that will work on the scientific and technological solutions that may contribute to solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

EDIH European Digital Innovation Hub

SoE See of Excellence

EELisa DIHs It refers to the EDIH or SOE mapped within the EELisa Alliance.

GA. Grant Agreement. This is the grant contract concluded between the EU and the beneficiaries. It establishes the rights and obligations that govern the grant. It consists of a core text and annexes (for instance, fixing the project content and the project budget).

KER. Key Exploitable Results. We refer to the research outputs with major potential for being exploited within the project.

KPIs. Key Performance Indicators

Project Results/ Project Outputs. By project results we understand a unit of knowledge that has been generated out of a project. This includes any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, prototypes, demonstrators, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected. It is not limited to pioneering discoveries, but may also include new methodologies/processes, adaptations, insights, alternative applications of prior knowledge. Along this document, we use project results and project outputs indistinctively, with the same meaning.

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1. Introduction to EELISA InnoCORE

The European Engineering Learning Innovation and Science Alliance (EELISA) is a bottom-up alliance of European higher education institutions representing more than 180,000 students and 50,000 graduates each year, 16,000 faculty members and 11,000 administrative staff. EELISA is one of the 41 European Universities selected by the European Commission under the Erasmus+ call, focused on education. EELISA was selected during the second pilot call. With the formalization of this European University, partners are initiating an unprecedented level of institutionalised cooperation between our institutions to gradually achieve our long-term ambitious vision: the education of European Engineers.

A pillar of EELISA will be the setting-up of EELISA Communities: challenge-based working groups where citizens, private companies and academia will collaborate to face societal challenges. EELISA Communities will be the place where education, research, innovation and public debate coexist and connect, enhancing the connection of engineering with society.

Within this framework, **EELISA InnoCORE is conceived as an integral part of the Alliance**, being a tool supporting, strengthening and delving deeper into the cooperation set up by EELISA. Building on the ecosystem of EELISA Communities, **EELISA InnoCORE focuses on the R&I dimension of the Alliance in a three-step plan**: 1) make our researchers and innovators know each other, create spaces for dialogue with citizens and with non-academic actors and set up a portfolio of shared scientific infrastructures; 2) foster and support the development of joint R&I actions and the creation of new structures (research groups, clusters, joint labs, start-ups, scientific parks) and 3) optimize the outreach of these actions.

EELISA InnoCORE will be running for three years, and it is structured around seven (7) work packages (WPs), focusing each on one of the key elements of the project. Under InnoCORE, EELISA partners will work on establishing a portfolio of joint research areas and defining a joint roadmap of research infrastructures (WP2). InnoCORE will map existing research infrastructures and facilities (WP4), with two aims: establishing the rules for opening their use and defining the main features of a booking system so that these resources can be used by all researchers of the Alliance, on the one hand; eventually, establishing a framework for jointly investing in new infrastructures.

EELISA InnoCORE will support the collaboration and the setting-up of joint research projects among the members of the Alliance through the development of a networking platform (WP5), the setting-up of clusters¹, the launching of seed funding for prospective young researchers (WP5) and the use of existing or new equipment and facilities in labs to foster collaborations (WP4). In addition to this, EELISA InnoCORE has two work packages dedicated to interlinking the incubation, start-up and entrepreneurship support services of the members of the alliance (WP7) and to foster the participation of society in science (WP7) and strengthening relations with the industry world (WP6). UPM will coordinate and lead the management of the project, being responsible for guiding the project in cross-cutting issues, such as gender balance (WP1). Lastly, the project has a dedicated work package on open science (WP3).

¹ Science-based working groups that will work on scientific and technological solutions than can help solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

WP	WP title	WP Leader
WP1	Coordination, evaluation, communication and dissemination	UPM
WP2	EELISA Research and Innovation Strategy	ITÜ
WP3	EELISA Strategic Framework for Open Science practices	UPB
WP4	EELISA Multi Labs (sharing facilities & equipment)	PSL
WP5	Set up initiatives for joint research projects (Enable joint research)	SNS
WP6	Reinforcing cooperation in R&I with other sectors, especially academia-business cooperation	BME
WP7	Create the "embedding" for EELISA-wide R&I structures (Optimize outreach)	FAU

Table 1: List of work packages and WP leaders

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2. European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIHs) and Seal of Excellence (SoE)

EELISA proposes to serve as an academic backbone linking a cohort of European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIHs) and Seal of Excellence (SoE) that have been fostered within the Digital Europe Programme to stimulate the broad uptake of Artificial Intelligence, High Performance Computing (HPC) and Cybersecurity as well as other digital technologies. The partners of the European Engineering Learning Innovation & Science Alliance are contributing to EDIHs and SoE initiatives in the respective countries in highly cross-disciplinary fields such as robotics, bioengineering and enabling information and communication technologies, and EELISA is contributing towards the strategic objective of establishing a pan-European EDIHs and SoE network with one hub per region. Specific actions towards this objective involve the deployment of the EELISA innoCORE Networking platform (TASK 5.1) to connect the communities (societal needs) and clusters (scientific and technological solutions) with the business opportunities mapped by the EDIHs. EELISA thus injects the EDIHs and SoE network with strategic competences, giving access to excellence research infrastructures (WP4) and educational programs (TASK 5.3), and providing highly qualified human capital graduated in strategic disciplines, filling the gap of the availability of qualified workforce in 4.0 domains and thus supporting the European digitalization strategy. EDIHs stimulate in turn within EELISA the setting-up of stable synergies between academia and businesses, with the purpose to fill the “valley of death” of technology Readiness Levels (TRL) from TRL 5 to TRL 7-8, to promote effective industrial application and the transformation of research into new products, creating highly qualified job opportunities.

2.1 Definition of Digital Innovation Hub

According to the EC², DIH is “one-stop-shops that help companies to become more competitive with regard to their business/production processes, products or services using digital technologies. They are based upon **technology infrastructure** (competence centre) and provide access to the latest knowledge, expertise and technology to support their customers with piloting, testing and experimenting with digital innovations. [...] As proximity is considered crucial, they act as a first regional point of contact, a doorway, and **strengthen the innovation ecosystem.**”

As Oliver et al pointed out (2020)³, “major strength of DIH programs is that they unify regionally-embedded relevant actors (such as universities, research centers, competence centers, private companies, incubators and start-up accelerators, clusters, governmental authorities, SMEs, investors and large organizations) to promote multipartner collaboration. DIHs focus primarily on SMEs, supporting them through the process of digitization of manufacturing. DIHs are the front office point to boost digital technologies for companies, offering digital technology testing or pilot project experimentation, acting as nodes to connect local networks of actors (chamber of commerce, universities, trade associations, accelerators, incubators, SMEs, startups, research organizations, investors, etc.) and providing also access to external-to-the-region actors.”

² <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/en/w/survey-on-potential-digital-innovation-hubs-dihs->

³ Hervás Oliver, J.L.; González-Alcaide, G.; Rojas-Alvarado, R.; Monto-Mompo, S. (2021). Emerging regional innovation policies for industry 4.0: analyzing the digital innovation hub program in European regions. *Competitiveness Review*. 31(1):106-129. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CR-12-2019-0159>

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Searching in the EDIH catalogue⁴, we count 398 EDIHs (75 Seal of Excellence, 151 hubs funded under Digital Europe Programme and 172 funded by other initiatives).

Figure 1 EDIH catalogue

Focusing on the EELISA countries (Spain, France, Italy, Germany, Romania, Hungary, and Turkey), we found total of 194 DIH (46 SoE, 68 hubs funded under Digital Europe Programme and 172 funded by other initiatives).

Figure 2 EDIH in EELISA Countries

⁴ [EDIH Catalogue | European Digital Innovation Hubs Network \(europa.eu\)](https://europa.eu)

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A recent report (2023)⁵ that describes the characteristics of the EDIHs at the European level, in terms of the most frequently addressed operational sectors are Manufacturing (64%), followed by Health Care (47%) and Public Sector (44%). For technologies, two of the Digital Europe Programme technologies are the most present: Artificial Intelligence is the dominant one (91%), followed by Cybersecurity (70%). The third most common technology covered by the EDIHs is Internet of Things (63%). Lastly, for the Services, the top ones are linked with SME support (81%) and Ecosystem building (72%) and Technological Innovation (71%).

2.2 Features of an EDIH

The main features of a European Digital Innovation Hub (EDIH) typically include dimensions as shown in next table. These features collectively contribute to the role of an EDIH in driving digital transformation and fostering innovation in various sectors.

Dimensions	Details
Technology Expertise	An EDIH is equipped with technological expertise in areas like artificial intelligence, data analytics, IoT, and other digital technologies.
Consultancy Services	It provides consultancy services to businesses and organizations seeking guidance on adopting and implementing digital solutions.
Training and Workshops	EDIHs often organize training programs and workshops to enhance the digital skills of individuals and teams within companies.
Access to Resources	They offer access to state-of-the-art digital tools, infrastructure, and resources, enabling businesses to experiment with and implement innovative technologies.
Networking Opportunities	EDIHs facilitate networking among businesses, academia, and research institutions, fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange.
Innovation Ecosystem	They contribute to building a local or regional innovation ecosystem by connecting various stakeholders and fostering a culture of innovation.
Research and Development Support	EDIHs may support collaborative research and development projects, bridging the gap between academic research and practical applications in the industry.
Technology Transfer	They assist in the transfer of technology and knowledge from research institutions to businesses, promoting the commercialization of innovative ideas.
Incubation and Acceleration	Some EDIHs offer incubation or acceleration programs to nurture and support startups focused on digital innovation.
Policy Advocacy	EDIHs may engage in advocating policies that promote digital innovation and collaboration within a region or industry.

Table 2 Dimension and features of an EDIH

Main actors, services and benefits of an EDIH (Sarripaia et al 2023)⁶ are listed in table 2.

⁵ De Nigris, S., Kalpaka, A. and Nepelski, D., Characteristics and regional coverage of the European Digital Innovation Hubs network, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2023, doi:10.2760/590526, JRC134620.

⁶ Sarraipa, Joao; Zamiri, Majid; Marcelino-Jesus, Elsa; Artifice, Andreia; Jardim-Goncalves, Ricardo; e altri. Computers; Basel Vol. 12, Fasc. 6, (2023): 122. DOI:10.3390/computers12060122

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Main Stakeholders	Main Supports and Services	Main Benefits for Companies
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public sectors • Government agencies • Private sector • Academia • NGOs • Chambers of commerce • Industrial sectors • Industry associations • Large companies • SMEs • Start-ups • Midcaps • Corporations • Extension agencies • Accelerators • Entrepreneurs • Real estate agents • Regional development agencies • Incubators/accelerators • Research centers • Living labs • Training institutes • Knowledge communities • Specialized experts • Mentors • Researchers • Students • Media • Suppliers • Investors 	<p><u><i>Innovation Activities and TT</i></u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness creation (e.g., about digital technologies, funding opportunities) • Digitalization • Digital maturity assessment • Digital transformation road-mapping • Developing technologies • Providing lab facilities • Access to infrastructure • Providing innovative solutions • Experimentation • Testing and validation • Concept validation and prototyping <p><u><i>Learning and Skill Development</i></u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training/mentoring • Sharing knowledge, experiences, and good practices • Developing skills • Access to specialist expertise • Advising (e.g., financing advice) • Collaborative research on issues of common interest <p><u><i>Business Development</i></u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supporting and strengthening businesses • Improving business/production processes, products, or services • Visioning and strategy development for businesses • Commercialization • Supporting incubation • Networking • Fostering relationships • Brokering/matchmaking • Connecting companies with investors • Linking suppliers with customers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding the company's needs • Identifying opportunities for digitization • Adapting advanced technologies • Transforming business • Developing business • Possessing significant know-how spanning • Developing and validating innovative solutions • Tackling innovation-related problems • Assessing digital maturity • Rapid access to consultative and expertise • Access to related roadshows, workshops, and innovation camps • Access to Funding and investor readiness services • Access to learning channels • Access to new knowledge and information • Access to tailored help and advice • Access to experimentation environments • Access to living labs for validating new business/products • Trying co-creation and synergy capture • Prototyping, testing, and implementing the solutions • Learning from experimenting • Being mentored about the issues such as trend analysis, business model development, value-chain creation, market assessments, internationalization • Training the workforce to be able to deal with the newly digitized processes, services, and products • Developing skills • Reducing risks

Table 3 Actors, services and benefits of an EDIH for companies

3. Mapping EDIHs and SoE in EELISA

The EELISA survey on European Digital Innovation Hubs and Seal of Excellence within the EELISA Alliance has the main aim to map the EDIHs within the EELISA Alliance and explore spaces for possible collaboration. In particular, the questionnaire has three main objectives:

1. to map the EDIHs within EELISA;
2. to deeper highlight the characteristics of the identified EDIHs;
3. to understand the possible spaces for collaboration between EELISA universities and EDIHs and among EDIHs.

The focus of the questionnaire are European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIH) and Seal of Excellence (SoE) that have been fostered under the Digital Europe Programme.

Considering the dimensions of an EDIH, a survey has been developed based on 8 sections. The complete questionnaire is reported on annex 1. The first section of the questionnaire is on the general characteristics of the EDIH/SoE. This section needs to identify a scientific contact person who can then answer the second part of the questionnaire (sections 2-8). After SSSA received the details of the contact persons, SSSA sent them sections 2-8. All questions are compulsory. Partners that are not involved in any EDIH were invited to send information on tentative proposal for an EDIH or any kind of similar experience in order to have a general overview of EELISA alliance on the issue.

3.1 Snapshot of the EELISA DIHs

Next table describes the EDIHs or SoE for each EELISA partner. UPM, SSSA, SNS, FAU, ITU and UPB have experience on EDIH. However, only UPM, SSSA, SNS and FAU are involved, in different ways and forms, in almost one EDIH each. SSSA is partner of two EDIHs. ITU and UPB have done several EDIHs proposal, without receiving funds. Table 3 describes EELISA InnoCORE overview on EDIHs experience.

EELISA University	EDIH or SoE
UPM	SoE Air4S (coordinator)
SSSA	EDIH ARTES 5.0 (partner and strong link to the coordinator)
FAU	EDIH DigiCare (link to a partner)
ENPC	No
PSL	No

UPB	UPB participated as a partner/coordinator with two proposals to develop an EDIH in the Bucharest-Ilfov region, and in an application for an EDIH in the N-E region, but no applications were selected.
BME	No
ITU	ITU participated in several proposals (see details)
SNS	Tuscany X.0 (partner) (SSSA is also involved as a partner)

Table 4 Experience of EELISA alliance in EDIHs

In the EDIH catalogue the EELISA EDIHs appear as in the next table.

EDIH DIGICARE (DIGICARE)	Germany	Anna Goldsworthy	3, Virtual Reality - 3	care - 5	innovation - 4, Technology transfer - 4
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Table 5 EELISA DIHs in the EDIH catalogue

ITU experience on DIH

Within the scope of the Digital Europe Program; the European Union (EU) is establishing European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIHs) and a network structure consisting of these hubs in order to support the digital transformation of industry, companies, especially SMEs, and public institutions. With the "Network of European Digital Innovation Hubs - Associated Countries (DIGITAL-2023-EDIH-04-ASSOCIATED)" call published on December 20, 2023, it is aimed to establish a similar structure in Turkey. The process is carried out by the Ministry of Industry and Technology and the Republic of Turkey. It is coordinated by the Presidential Digital Transformation Office.

Within the scope that mentioned above; "AI EDIH Turkey" as a large consortium formed under the coordination of MEXT Technology center applied to European Digital Innovation Centers Network – Associated Countries (DIGITAL-2023-EDIH-04-ASSOCIATED)" program on December 2023. MEXT Technology center (<https://www.mext.org.tr>) and ITU were listed as separate consortia leaders, but it was suggested that they merge the consortia. Project application preparations are currently continuing. The submission of the final application to the European Commission is scheduled for April 2024. Information regarding the project being applied for is listed below.

Project Name: AI EDIH Turkey: AI-Enabled Manufacturing for Twin Transition (AI EDIH Turkey) Consortium Members: MEXT Technology Center (Coordinator), İTÜ, İSO, Bilkent University, İSTKA, TÜBİTAK BİLGEM, 1773 İTÜ Science Park

Project Duration: 48 months

Project Budget: 1,996,042.20 EUR

- The maximum budget that can be requested is 2,000,000 Euros
- 50% co-financing obligation

3.2 Results of the Survey

The survey had the aim to explore the management and the and the functioning of the hubs on some specific aspects. This section provides an outline of the compared results of the hubs

in terms of services offered, relationship with the business community, and examples of success stories.

Eelisa University	EDIH or SoE	Location and year of establishment	Relation EDIH SoE and University	What is the primary mission of the EDIH/SoE?
 UPM	SoE Air4S direct connection	Madrid 2018	UPM is lead partner	AIR4S is established as a one-stop shop for private companies as well as public administration agencies in the Community of Madrid seeking comprehensive and multidisciplinary support for their digital transformation projects, by adopting artificial intelligence and robotics.
 SSSA	EDIH ARTES 5.0 direct connection	Pontedera (Pisa) 2022	SSSA is associated partner of Artes 5.0 and founding partner of Competence center Artes 4.0	ARTES 5.0 - Restart Italy promotes the widespread adoption of digital technologies, especially Robotics and Artificial Intelligence, to support sustainable, human-centric, and resilient value chains both for business system and public sector.
 FAU	EDIH DigiCare indirect connection	Erlangen 2023	Fau is not directly involved, but a premium partner of Medical Valley (one institution responsible for the EDIH)	The EDIH-DigiCare project aims to support small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and healthcare providers in their digital transformation. Through a variety of services, targeted assistance and resources are provided to overcome digital challenges and make the best possible use of the potential of digitalization in the healthcare sector.
 SNS and SSSA	EDIH Tuscany X.0 Direct connection	Pisa 2022	SNS and SSSA are funded beneficiaries	The opportunity of a Tuscany European Digital Innovation Hub (Tuscany X.0 -TX0) is the glue to federate many actors of the innovation and technology transfer into an ecosystem with an entrepreneurial mindset to guarantee an economical boost and growth beyond the EDIH timeframe.

Table 5 Main characteristics of EELISA EDIHs

3.2.1 Stakeholders and actors

The most common leading actors hosting or creating EDIHs are public organizations (research transfer office or University) or governmental (innovation or development) agencies. Also, other leading actors are private accelerators or public-private partnerships for research,

showing organizational structures such as joint ventures, network organizations (formal or informal) and projects with multi-partners with formalized end time. These are the case of EELISA EDIHs.

EDIH	Partners
EDIH ARTES 5.0	ARTES 4.0 (Coordinator), MedITech (Beneficiary), Start 4.0 (Beneficiary), CINI (Beneficiary), UniMORE (Affiliated Entity), PSTSicilia (Beneficiary), ISPRA (Beneficiary), I-RIM (Beneficiary), CICERO DIH Lazio (Beneficiary), DIH Toscana (Beneficiary), DIHA Umbria (Beneficiary), Symbola (Beneficiary), Intesa Sanpaolo (Beneficiary), Intesa Sanpaolo Innovation Center (Affiliated Entity), Intellera Consulting (Beneficiary), CNA (Beneficiary), Dintec (Beneficiary), Edi.it (Beneficiary), Fondazione Pico (Beneficiary), Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna (Associated Partner), INAIL (Associated Partner), Confartigianato (Associated Partner).
EDIH DigiCare	Medical Valley EMN e.V., Bayern Innovativ Gesundheit
EDIH Tuscany X.0	Polo Tecnologico, GATE4.0, DIH Toscana, Eurosportello, EDI.IT, Artes 4.0, CNR, School of High Studies Lucca, University of Florence, University of Pisa, University of Siena, Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, Scuola Normale Superiore.
SoE Air4S	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM); Accenture ESCP Business School; Spanish National Research Council (CSIC); Funding box; Madrid City Council Collaborating entities: Madrid Chamber of Commerce and Industry (Cámara de Madrid); Confederation of Employers and Industries of the Madrid Region (CEIM)

Table 6 Partners of EELISA EDIHs

3.2.2 Sectors and Services

As Oliver et al underline (2020)⁷, each EDIH is unique and formed by a particular set of local/regional agents with different interests, embedded in existing local/regional industrial bases. As such, depending on the local/regional industries, technologies and products embedded in each territory or location and the characteristics of the local companies/organizations involved, each DIH focuses on specific digital technologies and gives responses to different regional/local demands.

However, it is necessary to highlight that the nature of the services and orientation of the EELISA EDIHs is very similar with a strong emphasis on robotics and artificial intelligence as key enabling technologies to support local stakeholders, SMEs and public entities. Only one EDIH is focused on a single sector, that is DigiCare, which addresses the healthcare sector. The health sector, however, is a common sector to all EELISA EDIHs, a sign of a common and distinctive cluster of specialization for the Alliance.

The following table describes for each EDIHs/SoE the nature of the sectors addressed and the services provided.

⁷ Hervás Oliver, J.L.; González-Alcaide, G.; Rojas-Alvarado, R.; Monto-Mompo, S. (2021). Emerging regional innovation policies for industry 4.0: analyzing the digital innovation hub program in European regions. *Competitiveness Review*. 31(1):106-129. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CR-12-2019-0159>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

EELISA EDIH	Sectors	Services
AIR4S	Health and well being; 2. Energy, climate and Environment; 3. Mobility, transport and smart cities; 4. Industry 4.0 and manufacturing; Agrifood; Culture and education.	<p>1. Test before invest and technology services: access to AI & robotics infrastructures and resources; feasibility studies; proofs of concept (PoC); validation pilots in real conditions & operational environments; prototyping; technology adaptation and integration.</p> <p>2. Capacitation on technical & business skills: digital & AI maturity self-assessment; assessment on sustainability & ethical issues compliance in AI & robotics; mentoring on AI & robotics business plan development skills; technical skills training courses on AI data science & robotics; AI & robotics for business trianign courses; AI & robotics tech pills.</p> <p>3. Assessment on funding sources: assessment on public funding opportunities; training on innovation & cascade funding programmes; grant scan; connection with private investors.</p> <p>4. Ecosystems bulding: AIR4S awareness workshops; AI & robotics brokering innovation workshops; AI & robotics open innovation workshops; AIR4S online community service; EU ecosystem building on data economy and robotics.</p>
ARTES 5.0	1.health and quality of life (medical devices, intelligent machines for healthcare, precision medicine, well-being); 2. sustainable manufacturing (collaborative machines, safety at work); 3. regeneration economy (energy, transports, logistics, smart cities, agrifood, blue economy and Mediterranean topics);4. creative and cultural industry (crafts, tourism, fashion, cinematography, theater and cultural heritage).	<p>1. Test before invest services are the core of ARTES 5.0 and range from the digital assessment carried out with the expertise of industrial Digital Innovation Hubs to specialised test and experimentation provided by the partner competence and excellence centres.</p> <p>2. Training and skills development services cover both awareness-raising and orientation activities for supporting the digital and green twin transitions and vertical custom training on specific technologies and on organisational and cultural changes accompanying the digital transformation.</p> <p>3. Support to find investments services are available to help our customers to assess and get advised on financial aspects, business planning, IP and project development for accessing public funding, private financing and capital market. Match-making initiatives are also offered to ARTES 5.0 customers for finding investments supporting digital transformation.</p> <p>4. Innovation ecosystem and networking services aim at mapping and managing ecosystems of technology providers and adopters of digital solutions based on Robotics, Artificial Intelligence, and Industry 4.0 enabling technologies. Innovation ecosystems awareness and networking potential with local, national and EU initiatives are supported by the industrial Digital Innovation Hubs and the associations representing manufacturing and service SMEs and artisans.</p>
Digicare	Healthcare	<p>-Determination of the digital maturity level of SMEs and healthcare providers</p> <p>-Conducting reimbursement readiness checks and regulatory readiness checks</p> <p>-Access to test environments and test platforms</p>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Reducing time-to-market of products and services -Increasing the resilience of startups -Networking of healthcare providers and SMEs -Fostering transdisciplinary collaboration and co-creation -Solving real-world challenges through Open Innovation Challenges -Advising on R&D funding and investments -Training and competence development within the framework of the DigiCare Academy -Expansion of networking and digital interaction through events -Implementation of a trend and technology radar -Establishment of a competence network MDR & IVDR -Support in the acquisition of digital natives
SNS and Tuscany X.0	<p>1-Manufacturing and Aerospace and Defence: automotive, transport, fashion (textile, apparel), jewellery, leather and tanning, chemistry, paper, nautical sector, stone and marble machineries, construction sector, interior design, aeronautics, space, defence and security industries. 2- Healthcare: pharmaceutical sector (vaccines, medicines), medical device industry. 3- Cultural Heritage and Wellness: logistics, precision agriculture, cultural and creative industry, food, agri-food, tourism.</p>	<p>1) Services to assess its DML and builds confidence and to support the user in the use of DMA tool. 2) Test before Invest services in AI - Implementation of the AI-based services to overcome the specific challenge (Feasibility study,Engineering and Data,Industrial Co-creation). 3) Test before Invest services in CS - Implementation of the CS technologies-based services to overcome the challenges (Identify,Protect,Detect,Respond,Recover). 4) Test before Invest services in HPC - Implementation of the HPC technologies-based services to overcome the challenges (Awareness,Feasibility study, Application Sampling,Testing of Specific Systems,Systems benchmark,Application sampling). 5) Test before Invest services for accelerating the best use of (other) digital/green technologies - Services (or part of) enabling/completing the implementation of services within Industry 4.0, green data space,blockchain,new PA platforms solutions will be made available</p>

Table 7 Sectors and Services of EELISA EDIHs

AIR4S

Considering the AIR4S, the picture shows in sectors and specialized center.

experience of the SoE a simple way specific technologies of the

Figure 3 Sector and Areas for AIR4S

3.2.3 Access to

the EDIHs

Considering the procedure to access EDIHs services is important for ensuring transparency, efficiency, tailored support and quality assurance. Considering the EDIHs in EELISA, the procedures for accessing the hubs are different and involve different types of steps from the simplest, such as an initial contact via email (type) to more comprehensive procedures (such as AIR4S). Descriptions of AIR4S, ARTES 5.0, and Tuscany X.0 are given as examples. AIR4S, TuscanyX.0, and ARTES 5.0 have an online form in order to collect data and information; second step is the assessment of the digital maturity.

AIR4S

The Digital innovation Hub AIR4S acts as a one-stop shop for SMEs and start-ups. Below you will find a figure describing the process to access the services (this refers particularly to contracting services related to Test before investing and technology services):

1. For getting in contact (*atención e información general*), AIR4S has the following channels: A physical office where B2B meetings can take place (at UPM's rectorate); an online form; an email adress.
2. As a second step after the first contact, there is an analyses and diagnosis, (*diagnóstico y asesoramiento preliminar*) of the needs of the company or start-up regarding the services and resources needed, or needs on skills or knowledge.
3. Once the diagnosis has been run, AIR4S tries to connect the company with the relevant provider in the ecosystem (relevant member of AIR4S). For this, AIR4S follows an internal procedure called "Protocol for allocation of services" (*protocolo de asignación de servicios*).
4. The provider identified continues the process and the contact with the company from this point (*conexión con proveedor y asesoramiento específico*).

Figure 4 Access to AIR4S

ARTES 5.0

Are you an SME owner? ARTES 5.0 will help you to find the most **suitable digital solutions** for your company available within the **ARTES 5.0 Charter of Services**

Book an appointment with our specialists

The EDIH customers can directly contact the coordinator of the EDIH by filling out a form, which is different in case of a company or a Public Sector Organization, to submit a support request. The EDIH coordinator assess the request to direct the customer towards the service provider, following internal EDIH procedures. The EDIH customers can also get in contact to one of the EDIH partners (Beneficiaries) for a direct liaison tailored at receiving one/several service(s).

Figure 5 Access Artes 5.0

TUSCANY X.0

The model of Tuscany X.0 is based on several collaborations. The process used follows a lean methodology which, thanks to a well-defined process, will bring real benefit to businesses and public administrations.

Through Access Points, i.e., reception desks reception desks, requests will be channelled to the System Integrators who will analyze the need and will indicate the most suitable partner, the Provider, who can be able to meet the needs that emerge. A true team effort to make the Tuscany increasingly competitive in

responding the challenges of digital transformation.

Figure 6 Access to Tuscany X.0

3.2.4 Collaboration, Networking and Research

Overall, EELISA EDIHs serve as catalysts for collaboration and innovation, driving economic growth and competitiveness within the European Union by bringing together businesses, academia, and research institutions to address common challenges and seize opportunities in the digital age. Considering the experience of the EELISA EDIHs, three are the main tools to work towards collaboration, networking and research:

1. **Training sessions and programs** and workshops to help businesses and stakeholders to acquire the skills and knowledge needed to thrive in the digital economy. This includes training in areas such as digital technologies, entrepreneurship, innovation management, and project management.

For example, AIR4S regularly organizes training sessions on funding sources which are also conceived as networking spaces: in addition to providing training, the aim of the sessions is to give start-ups, SMEs and other participants the opportunity to meet peers and meet relevant stakeholders, including public authorities. There is an average of 8 training sessions per year.

2. **Networking Platforms and events:** EDIHs and SoEs serve as networking platforms, bringing together stakeholders from various sectors such as industry, academia, and research. They organize events, workshops, and conferences where these stakeholders can meet, share knowledge, and build partnerships.

For example Digicare organizes open innovation challenges where, among other participants, students can take part, such as hackathons and ideation days.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

For example every month Tuscany X.0 organizes training event and webinar dedicated to special issue related to digital transformation. Here an example of a webinar dedicated to the “Metaverso for the Hospitality sector” organized in October 2023.

Figure 7 Event

for Tuscany X.0

3. **Collaborative Projects:** They support collaborative projects between businesses, academia, and research institutions. By fostering collaboration, these hubs facilitate the co-creation of knowledge, the development of innovative

solutions, and the commercialization of research findings.

For example ARTES 5.0 and Tuscany X.0, under the Open Innovation dimension, provide services that promote and support strategies and collaborative projects aimed at developing ideas, solutions, tools and technological competences within the open innovation framework. This support is a free service.

For example ARTES 5.0 dedicates a whole Work Package to the establishment and consolidation of long-term partnerships between ARTES 5.0 and other EDIHs at the national and European level, including collaborations with Academic, Research and Innovation Institutions.

3.2.5 KPI, monitoring and evaluation system

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are essential for measuring the impact of a Digital Innovation Hub (DIH). These KPIs help assess the effectiveness of the DIH in achieving its objectives and delivering value to stakeholders. Additionally, regular monitoring and evaluation of KPIs can help identify areas for improvement and guide strategic decision-making to enhance the effectiveness of the DIH. Here are some examples and common KPIs to measure the impact of the EELISA EDIHs.

EELISA EDIHs	KPIs
Tuscany x.0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of businesses and public sector entities, which have used the EDIHs' services per user category, sector, location and type of support received; - Amount of additional investments successfully triggered (e.g. through venture capital, bank loan, etc.); - Number of collaborations with other EDIHs and stakeholders outside the region at EU level, and description of jointly shared infrastructures / joint investments with other EDIH.(section 3.1,table 1,"TX0 users served by other EDIHs", "users beyond the EDIH served by TX0"); - Increase in digital maturity of those organizations that have used the services of the EDIH network; - Market maturity and market creation potential of innovations, as defined in the JRC's Innovation Radar methodology.
AIR4S	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of services included in the market place. - Number of SMEs, start-ups and companies having requested and used AIR4S' technological services. - Number of entrepreneurship projects and ideas supported. - Number of trainings on skills on Artificial Intelligence and Robotics organised. - Number of SMEs, start-ups and companies having attended the trainings on AI and robotic skills. - Number of trainings and sessions on funding opportunities and internationalisation organised. - Number of SMEs, start-ups and companies having attended the sessions on funding opportunities and internationalisation. - Number of events attended by AIR4S partners to promote Madrid ecosystem.
ARTES 5.0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Number of services provided, -Number of the EDIH customers (companies and/or Public Sector Organizations) supported, -Amount of financial support "transferred" to the EDIH customers.
Digicare	Number of SMEs

Table 8 KPIs of EELISA EDIHs

In terms of KPIs, it is noted that the monitoring and evaluation process is recognized as crucial among EDIHs and occurs regularly. Despite this, the indicators brought as examples often refer to input or output data. Very much in the minority are outcome and impact measures that could measure, directly and indirectly, the value to society of EDIHs.

In this sense, by the discussion within the EELISA EDIHs, some KPIs that could be defined in dictate and measure are:

- **Revenue Generated:** Track the revenue generated by businesses as a result of their involvement with the EDIH. This could include revenue from new products, services, or processes developed through EDIH-supported initiatives.
- **Funding Leveraged:** Track the amount of funding leveraged by businesses through EDIH-supported projects, including public funding, private investment, and EU funding sources such as Horizon Europe.
- **Intellectual Property (IP) Generation:** Measure the creation and protection of intellectual property resulting from EDIH-supported initiatives, including patents filed, licenses issued, and technology transfer agreements signed.

3.2.6 Success Story

A success story for an EDIH typically exhibits several key features that demonstrate the effectiveness and impact of the EDIHs in driving innovation, collaboration, and economic

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growth, such as Collaborative Ecosystem, Technology Advancement, Funding and Investment and Business Impact. Considering the experience of EELISA EDIHs, a case from AIR4S is detailed as follows. This case underlines both the collaborative ecosystem (considering that the target here is a public administration) and the developed solution in terms of technology advancement.

➔ AIR4S Open data for citizen participation and transparency City of Zaragoza, Office of Public Participation and Transparency.

The Office for Public Participation and Transparency of the city of Zaragoza needed to improve the way in which they published their open data, moving from a 3-star open data sharing in their open data catalogue and open data API into a 5-star open data sharing, according to the 5-star model for open data publication from Tim Berners-Lee. For this, they needed support to enable their open data API to publish RDF in the RDF/XML, Turtle and JSON-LD formats, as well as consultancy on the development of ontologies on which such data may be based.

UPM provided two different types of services: ontology development for smart cities, focusing on the ontologies and vocabularies that can be used for the publication of open data in 4 and 5 star formats; and improvement of the legacy source code used in the open data API of Zaragoza so as to enable the creation of annotations to generate RDF in different formats.

• 4 Elaborating EDIHs and SoE in EELISA

4.1 Network Event

Networking events that connect different EDIHs play a vital role in fostering collaboration, knowledge sharing, ecosystem building, market expansion, policy influence, and capacity building. They contribute to the growth and development of a vibrant digital innovation ecosystem. In this sense, under the EELISA Innocore project a first networking event was organized to connect the mapped EELISA EDIHs and SoE. The event was organized on February 26, 2024, in online mode and was attended by ARTES 5.0 (Paolo Dario, Calogero Oddo, and Rossella Raso), AIR4S (Isabel Salguero); Digicare (David Schkade for FAU, Timm Ehbauer for Digicare).

Figure 8 Picture of the online event

After a brief presentation of each hub, the discussion focused on the possible benefits of being part of university institutions that constitute an alliance. In general, the focus was on the possible collaborations in terms of shared access to industry contacts to co-promote the

expertise and services of the hub and of access to the international network of experts and to the shared infrastructure, as also Tuscany X.0 stated in the survey.

Considering the point of view of ARTES 5.0, this hub supports the formalization of partnerships/collaborations with EDIH related to the EU Alliances, and, in particular the EELISA Alliance, with the purpose of serving as an academic backbone linking a cohort of EDIHs and injecting the EDIH network with strategic competences, giving access to excellent research infrastructures and educational programs, and providing highly qualified human capital graduated in strategic disciplines, filling the gap of the availability of qualified workforce in 4.0 domains and thus supporting the European digitalization strategy.

Digicare also stresses the importance of organizing events such as open innovation challenges or informational sessions.

Air4S undelines the importance of establishing links to collaborate in different areas, such as:

- R&I projects.
- Training sessions.
- Providing AI&Robotics expertise in other EELISA initiatives.
- Participation in common EU projects.
- Sharing of knowledge and expertise.
- Sharing of infrastructures.
- Access to new market opportunities for SMEs supported.

In the following section we summarize the possible benefits for the EELISA EDIHs to be part of the EELISA Alliance and viceversa as emerged in the survey, during the networking event and considering also the EELISA Innocore project.

4.2 Benefits of being a Digital Innovation Hubs within the EELISA alliance

Considering the framework of EDIHs and SoE within the EELISA alliance we can identify three ways in which centers and the alliance can benefit mutually: 1. the contribution of each hub toward the university alliance; 2. the contribution of the university alliance toward each hub; 3. the contribution among the different hubs. This could be represented in a sort of triangulation of benefits and value added.

Figure 9 Triangulation of benefits

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I.EELISA → The EELISA alliance can contribute to the EELISA EDIHs/SoE in these ways:

1. **Access to Academic Expertise:** Universities within EELISA can provide access to a diverse range of academic expertise across various disciplines. This expertise can be valuable for conducting research, developing new technologies, and solving complex problems within the EELISA EDIH/SoE.
2. **Collaborative Research Opportunities:** EELISA Universities engage in cutting-edge research relevant to the goals and objectives of EELISA EDIHs. By forming partnerships with universities in the alliance, the EELISA EDIHs may collaborate on research projects, share resources, and access funding opportunities to drive innovation and advance knowledge.
 - a. EELISA Innocore project has developed the EELISA networking platform for researchers together with a subcontractor that is an SME of ARTES 4.0. This collaboration brought the ARTES 5.0 center closer to the EELISA Alliance, enabling an exchange of knowledge and expertise that brings added value to both the Alliance and the DIH.
 - b. Connection with EELISA2 WP9 “EELISA’s Network for Researchers and Talent”.
3. **Student Talent Pool:** EELISA EDIHs can tap into student talent pool by offering internship programs, co-op placements, and collaborative research opportunities for students. This not only benefits the EDIHs by providing access to skilled and motivated individuals but also offers students valuable hands-on experience and exposure to real-world challenges.
4. **Access to Facilities and Infrastructure:** EELISA have state-of-the-art facilities, laboratories, and research infrastructure that can support the activities of the EELISA EDIHs (see also WP4). By partnering with universities in the alliance, the EELISA EDIHs can get access to these resources, enabling their customers to conduct experiments, prototype new technologies, and test innovative solutions in a controlled environment.
5. **Entrepreneurship and Innovation Ecosystem:** EELISA has strong entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystems (see also WP 7 of EELISA Innocore and EELISA 2 WP10 Innovation and Entrepreneurship Ecosystem) that supports startup formation, technology transfer, and commercialization activities. By collaborating with these institutions, the EELISA EDIHs can leverage their networks, mentorship programs, and funding opportunities to support startups, facilitate technology transfer, and drive economic growth.
 - a. Digicare will participate in the EELISA Next Level Event (funding Booster Event) organized by FAU. In a future edition, this type of event will be open to Startups from MedicalValley and Digicare.
Connection with WP 7 EELISA Innocore
6. **Educational and Training Programs:** Universities within the alliance can collaborate with the EDIHs to develop educational and training programs that address the needs of industry and society. This can include workshops, seminars, and certificate programs on topics such as digital literacy, emerging technologies, and innovation management, designed to upskill professionals and promote lifelong learning.

II.Hubs → The EELISA EDIHs can contribute to the EELISA alliance in these ways.

1. **Research Collaboration:** EDIHs often serve as centers for cutting-edge research and development. Through collaboration with a university alliance, these hubs can leverage the expertise of multiple institutions to tackle complex challenges, conduct interdisciplinary research, and explore new avenues of innovation.

- a. Eelisa Innocore project has developed the Eelisa networking platform for researchers together with a subcontractor that is a SME of ARTES 5.0. This collaboration brought the ARTES 5.0 center closer to the EELISA Alliance, enabling an exchange of knowledge and expertise that brings added value to both the Alliance and the DIH. Connection with WP5.

2. **Knowledge Transfer and Exchange:** EELISA Universities can share their research findings, methodologies, and best practices with the EELISA EDIHs. In return, the hubs can disseminate this knowledge to industry partners, startups, and other stakeholders, fostering technology transfer and promoting economic growth.
3. **Entrepreneurship and Startups:** University alliances often have strong connections to entrepreneurship ecosystems and startup communities. An EDIH can collaborate with these networks to support aspiring entrepreneurs, provide access to funding opportunities, mentorship, and incubation services, and facilitate the commercialization of research and innovation.
4. **Community Engagement and Outreach:** EELISA EDIHs can serve as hubs of activity, bringing together researchers, students, industry professionals, policymakers, and the broader community. By partnering with the EELISA alliance, these hubs can extend their reach and impact, hosting events, conferences, and networking opportunities that promote collaboration, knowledge exchange, and collective problem-solving.
5. **Policy and Advocacy:** EELISA EDIHs can advocate for policies and initiatives that support digital transformation, innovation, and entrepreneurship. By aligning with a university alliance, these hubs can leverage the collective expertise and influence of multiple institutions to shape policy agendas, inform decision-making, and promote a conducive environment for innovation and growth.

III.EELISA EDIHs → EELISA EDIHs. Different EDIHs can collaborate in various ways to leverage their respective strengths and resources for mutual benefit and to achieve common goals. Moreover, if the EDIHs belong to the same University Alliance, the synergy is much more effective. Here are some examples of collaboration.

1. **Knowledge Sharing and Best Practices:** EDIHs can establish networks or consortia where they regularly exchange information, share best practices, and learn from each other's experiences. This can include organizing workshops, seminars, or webinars focused on specific topics related to digital innovation, technology trends, or industry developments.

The EELISA EDIHs survey and the networking meeting of February 26 is a good example of this type of collaboration.

2. **Cross-Referral and Partnership Opportunities:** EDIHs can refer clients, startups, or projects to each other based on their areas of specialization or expertise. They can also collaborate on client projects or form partnerships to offer comprehensive solutions that leverage the strengths of multiple hubs.

3. **Ecosystem Development:** EDIHs can work together to build and strengthen the broader innovation ecosystem in their region or industry vertical. This can include collaborating with local government agencies, industry associations, educational institutions, and other stakeholders to support entrepreneurship, attract investment, and foster innovation-driven economic development.
4. **Joint Events and Conferences:** Collaborating EDIHs can organize joint events, conferences, or hackathons to promote knowledge exchange, networking, and collaboration among stakeholders. These events can provide opportunities for startups to showcase their innovations, for investors to discover new opportunities, and for researchers to present their findings.
5. **International Partnerships:** EELISA EDIHs can also explore opportunities for international collaboration by partnering with similar organizations in other countries or regions. This can facilitate knowledge transfer, market expansion, and access to global talent, funding, and markets.

Between December 2021 and February 2022, during the preparation of the proposal “ARTES 5.0 Restart Italy”, the Scientific Coordinator, Paolo Dario, Professor Emeritus at Scuola Superiore Sant’Anna and Scientific Director of ARTES 4.0, sent several messages to the contact persons for other European Digital Innovation Hub (EDIH) proposals as a first attempt to establish a cooperation with them.

At the time of writing of the proposal, the EDIHs catalogue listed all the EDIH proposals grouped by Country, Technologies and Sector. Indeed, back to 2021 this catalogue listed all the EDIH proposals that were pre-selected at the national level by the EU Member States.

ARTES 5.0 browsed the catalogue by filtering the Countries located in the Southern Europe/Mediterranean area, such as Croatia, Cyprus, France, Germany, Greece, Israel, Malta, Portugal, Romania, Slovenia, and Spain. Among the EDIH proposals inquired, only the

62 EDIH proposals with expertise in Robotics and AI (as signature Technology) were contacted.

ARTES 5.0 signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with 19 EDIH proposals of the 62 contacted before the Call DIGITAL-2021-EDIH-INITIAL-01 cut-off date.

The objectives of the signed MoUs are the following: to address common challenges as a means of exploitation of the unfulfilled developmental capacity in border areas by leveraging EDIHs complementarities; to share models for effective technology transfer, services, and networking; to share best practices for creating highly effective ecosystems in the Southern Europe/Mediterranean area and to connect with other EU regions; to relocate users requiring services in AI and Robotics technologies for a better geographical proximity; to relocate users requiring services in domain where expertise is lacking; to share/exchange services in Skills and Training; to share complementary facilities for Test-Before-Invest; to share best practices on financing innovation. In the end, the MoUs signed by ARTES 5.0 are with 9 EDIHs and 5 SoEs. The remaining 5 MoUs were signed with EDIH proposals which did not submit the proposal to the EU Call.

ARTES 5.0 – Beyond Italy, towards Europe

ARTES 5.0 is open to establish **long-term partnerships with other EDIHs** in Italy and neighboring regions abroad, sharing the technological focus on Artificial Intelligence and Robotics.

+20 Collaborations (MoUs) signed with EDIHs in EuroMed9 area and Mediterranean countries.

Figure 10 ARTES 5.0 Connections

Considering the experience of ARTES 5.0 and the EELISA Alliance, Annex 2 to this deliverable represent a draft multilateral Memorandum of Understanding with the 4 Hubs identified. This memorandum of understanding is under discussion among the

partners with the aim to be signed by all EELISA EDIHs.

4.3 Long-term collaboration between EDIHs/SoE and EELISA

Despite the EELISA InnoCORE project is finishing in May 2024, the path for collaboration with EDIHs/SoE initiated in the framework of the project will continue. EDIHs will be operating at least until the end of 2025 and the EC has already announced a roll-out phase for the following 3-4 years.

EELISA InnoCORE will merge in EELISA 2 WP “EELISA’s Network for Researchers and Talent”, which aims at connecting facilities, their researchers, and providing young talents with the necessary skills to excel in their future careers, contributing to the organic and synergistic growth of joint research initiatives within the Alliance and to the establishment and reinforcement of a network of talents, increasing the attractiveness and competitiveness of EELISA partners.

Annex I - Questionnaire on European Digital Innovation Hubs and Seal of Excellence

PART 1

Section 1: General Information

- 1.1. Name of the European Digital Innovation Hub or Seal of Excellence:
- 1.2. Location:
- 1.3. Year of Establishment:
- 1.4. EDIH/SoE:
- 1.5. Institutions and partners involved:
- 1.6. Name and e-mail of a coordinator/scientific responsible to be contacted:
- 1.7. Website:
- 1.8. Please, detail the relationship between the EDIH/SoE and the your University:

PART 2

Section 2: Mission and Objectives

- 2.1. What is the primary mission of the EDIH/SoE?
- 2.2. List the main objectives the EDIH/SoE aims to achieve.

Section 3: Services Offered and Technology Expertise

- 3.1.1 Please provide a brief overview of the key services offered by the EDIH/SoE.
- 3.2. Does the EDIH/SoE focus on specific sectors? If yes, please specify.
- 3.3. What digital technologies does the EDIH/SoE specialize in?

Section 4: Collaboration, Networking and Research

- 4.1. Explain how the EDIH/SoE facilitates collaboration among businesses, academia, and research institutions.
- 4.2. Are there regular networking events or platforms organized by the EDIH/SoE?
- 4.3. Does the DIH support collaborative research and development projects? If yes, please specify how.

Section 5: Innovation Ecosystem, Incubation/Acceleration and Technology Transfer

- 5.1. Describe how the EDIH/SoE contributes to building the local/regional innovation ecosystem.
- 5.2. Can you share any success stories of businesses or startups that have benefited from the EDIH/SoE 's support?
- 5.3. What specific resources and support are available for startups within the EDIH/SoE?
- 5.4. How does the EDIH/SoE facilitate the transfer of technology and knowledge from research and academia to businesses?

Section 6: Monitoring and Evaluation

- 6.1. How does the EDIH/SoE measure the impact of its services and activities?

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6.2. Are there key performance indicators (KPIs) that the EDIH/SoE tracks regularly?

Section 7: Membership and Access

7.1. Which is the procedure to access the DIH services?

7.2. What criteria or requirements are in place for accessing the EDIH/SoE's resources and services?

Section 8: Future Plans and EELISA

8.1. How does the EDIH/SoE envision its role in the EELISA Alliance?

8.2. How the EDIH/SoE can benefit from EELISA?

8.3. How EELISA can benefit from EDIH/SoE?

8.4. Are there any upcoming initiatives or expansions planned jointly with EELISA for the EDIH/SoE?

**Annex II Multilateral Memorandum of Understanding –
template-**

MEMORANDUM OF UNDERSTANDING
between

The European Digital Innovation Hub (EDIH) ARTES 5.0 established in Pontedera (Pisa), Italy represented by ARTES 4.0 (Advanced Robotics and enabling digital TEchnologies and Systems 4.0), “ARTES 5.0” “Party 1”

and

The European Digital Innovation Hub DigiCARE.....established inrepresented by....., “Party 2”

and

The European Digital Innovation Hub Tuscany X.0.....established inrepresented by....., “Party 3”

and

The Seal of Excellence AIR4S.....established inrepresented by....., “Partner 3” “Party 4”

Accordingly, the Parties agree as follows

Background

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

The Parties are members of the European network of Digital Innovation Hubs and Seal of Excellence established across 2022 and 2023 under the Digital Europe Program as the result of the restricted Call European Digital Innovation Hubs ([DIGITAL-2021-EDIH-01](#)), “the Call”.

ARTES 5.0 and DigiCare were selected under the Call and received a three-year co-funding from the European Commission (EC) and their Member States, that are the Italian Ministry for Enterprises and Made in Italy and the German

AIR4S received the “Seal of Excellence” for the high quality of the proposal submitted to the Call but did not get the funding from the EC. AIR4S is fully financed by for a three-year (?) period.

ARTES 5.0 offers innovation services to small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and Public Sector Organizations to accelerate their twin (digital and green) transitions and promote the widespread adoption of digital technologies, especially Robotics and Artificial Intelligence, to support sustainable, human-centric, and resilient value chains.

The EDIH-DigiCare project aims to support small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and healthcare providers in their digital transformation. Through a variety of services, targeted assistance and resources are provided to overcome digital challenges and make the best possible use of the potential of digitalization in the healthcare sector.

AIR4S is established as a one-stop shop for private companies as well as public administration agencies in the Community of Madrid seeking comprehensive and multidisciplinary support for their digital transformation projects, by adopting artificial intelligence and robotics.

Purpose

The Parties express their interest to a long-term collaboration to explore and facilitate synergy and opportunities for exchange of good practices, expertise, knowledge, and other possible assets in the areas of mutual interest, with focus on Artificial Intelligence and Robotics, for a sustainable and equitable development to face societal challenges along with EELISA innoCORE and EELISA 2 mission.

Subject matter

The Parties recognize the relevance of a collaboration leveraging the EELISA network which aims to serve as an academic backbone linking a cohort EDIH and stimulate the broad uptake of Artificial Intelligence, Robotics, and other key enabling technologies in support of the digital and green (twin) transitions for Companies and Public Sector Organizations.

Although each EDIH/SoE is unique and led by a particular set of local/regional agents with different interests, embedded in existing local/regional societal context, this Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) aims at setting the stage for possible collaborations according to the following actions/activities:

- Sharing models for effective technology transfer, services, and networking;
- Sharing best practices for creating highly effective ecosystems in EU regions;
- Sharing users that could find a better geographical coverage in the partners;
- Joint staff recruitment and exchange of personnel for short visiting periods to share good practices, joint training of staff;
- Supporting the targeting dissemination of recruitment calls;
- Sharing and exchange services in skills and for training;
- Sharing complementary facilities for test-before-invest;
- Sharing good practices on financing innovation;
- Sharing access to networks of investors;
- Organizing periodically events and meeting to discuss synergies, possibilities and new collaborations also considering the benefits of being part of the EELISA Alliance.
- Sharing and updating a page on the EELISA website with information on the synergy established between EELISA and the EDIH network.

Duration and obligations

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This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

This MoU does not impose any financial or capital obligations on the Parties. It is intended to describe the nature and suggest the guidelines of cooperation as described. Therefore, nothing affects the full autonomy of either institution, or will any constraints be imposed on the others in carrying out what is signed. The Parties will therefore ensure to adopt any necessary measure to achieve the objectives concerning the collaboration in complete fiscal, administrative and operational autonomy.

This agreement will take effect upon signature by the Parties and will remain in force until December 31, 2025. Three months (90 days) before the expiring date of this MoU, the Parties will be called to decide whether to extend this agreement and how long. Revisions and amendments shall be made by mutual agreement. A Party may at any time withdraw from the MoU and terminate its involvement in the activities set out in this MoU. Such termination shall be done in writing to all other Parties. Any dispute that might arise concerning this MoU shall be settled amicably.

Intellectual property right

The Parties agree that this MoU do not grant or imply any license, interest or right to the Recipient in respect to any intellectual property right of the other Party. The Parties acknowledge that nothing in this MoU shall affect ownership of any intellectual property rights.

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